

Microcanonical Derivation of the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution?

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In statistical mechanics texts, a canonical approach using maximization is often used to derive the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. In this note, we attempt to use a microcanonical approach to calculate the distribution and find it leads to the same MB form if one uses Stirling's approximation.

Microcanonical Approach to MB Distribution

Consider a system with N particles and a total energy E . In addition, one needs an energy density of single particle states to solve this problem. For the MB case with $E=p^2/2m$, where p is momentum, the energy density is d^3p/V with $\hbar=1$. Consider E/a as being the smallest amount of energy that may be transferred in a two particle collision. " a " is very small, making " E " extremely large. Next, let V be the number of "segments" of energy in the system. Each segment is associated with a single particle energy e and an energy density d^3p/V with $\hbar=1$. Thus, one needs to use V segments and not N , the number of particles, in the calculation. Then, one may find a probability $P(e)$ associated with a segment which has d^3p/V particles, all with energy e .

If one has E/a units of energy and V segments, the question becomes one of distributing the E/a units into the V segments. This may be done using a factorial scheme which interestingly enough is usually associated with the calculation of the Bose-Einstein distribution (1). One considers $V-1$ inner boundary walls (there are 2 fixed outer boundary walls) with E/a energy units and permutes, dividing by $(V-1)!$ And $(E/a)!$ I.e.:

$$\text{Number of microcanonical arrangements} = \frac{[E/a + V - 1]!}{[(V-1)! (E/a)!]} \quad ((1))$$

Next, one imagines removing a single particle with energy e and momentum p in a particular direction. The direction of p does not matter because one assumes all p directions have equal probability. Then:

$$\text{Number of arrangements with an } e \text{ out} = \frac{[E/a - e/a + V - 1]!}{[(V-1)! (E/a - e/a)!]} \quad ((2))$$

$E/a \gg V$ because one is distributing many E/a energy units into V boxes.

Taking the \ln of ((2)) and using Stirling's approximation because numbers are very large due to " a " (not necessary N being large) one has:

$$\ln(P(e)) = [E/a - e/a + V - 1] \ln[E/a - e/a + V - 1] - (E/a - e/a) \ln[(E/a - e/a)] - (V-1) \ln(V-1) \quad ((3))$$

Using, to first order in e : $\ln[E/a - e/a + V - 1] = \ln(E/a + V - 1) - (e/a) / [(E/a + V - 1)]$ and keeping only terms related to e (because the others will become part of a normalization constant) yields:

$\ln(P(e)) = -(e/a) \ln[(E/a+V-1)/(E/a)]$ or $P(e) = [1+ (V-1)/(E/a)]^{-e/a}$
 Given that $E/a \gg V-1$, $[1+(V-1)/(E/a)] = \exp[(V-1)/(E/a)]$ so:

$$P(e) \exp[-(V-1) e/E] \quad ((4))$$

Thus, the result does not depend on “a” and is of a Maxwell-Boltzmann form. One may use normalization to determine $E/(V-1)$ i.e. it is found to be equal to temperature.

It should be noted that ((4)) applies to a single particle with energy e. In the microcanonical approach there is a correlation between particles because there is a fixed amount of total energy E. If one particle has a large portion of this energy, it restricts what other particles may have.

Maximum Uncertainty of a Single Particle Energy in Time

It is interesting to note that the above approach which calculates P(e) from microcanonical macrostates yields the same result as the consideration of a single particle in time with the probability m_i of having energy e_i . If one wishes to maximize the uncertainty of this energy arrangement in time, one may maximize:

$\ln[M! / (m_1! m_2! \dots)] + b \sum e_i m_i$ where b is a Lagrange multiplier and M the number of time slices. The constraint is related to the idea that one average, a single particle will have E/N of the energy. This time-maximum uncertainty of energy approach thus seems to be equivalent to the microcanonical one, at least when the Stirling approximation is made. The microcanonical approach, however, does not involve any maximization calculation while the time-maximum uncertainty one does.

Canonical Considerations

One may argue that it would be possible to keep Order(e^*e) terms in the expansion of “ln”, but one would then also need to possibly consider higher order terms of the Stirling approximation. Thus, it is possible to obtain corrections to the MB distribution.

From this approach one obtains the single particle MB distribution $P(e) = C \exp(-e/T)$. It is then traditional to treat all single particles as being the same and create a “partition” function:

$$[\sum \text{over } i \ C \exp(-e_i/T)]^N \quad ((5))$$

This is proportional to: $\sum \text{over } E \ \exp(-E/T)$ where $E = \sum \text{over } i \ e_i$ ((6)). This is the canonical approach because one no longer fixes E, there is only an E average and variance.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have attempted to provide a microcanonical derivation for the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution which differs from canonical approaches which usually appear. We find to first order in ϵ that one again obtains the MB form.

References

1. Huang, K. Statistical Mechanics (Wiley, 1983) page 182